

Blue Shift in the Absorption Spectra of Fluorescein Anion and Excited-state Lifetimes¹

Miss K. K. Rohatgi

The absorption spectrum of fluorescein anion has been measured in a number of solvents. A blue shift is observed with increasing dielectric constant of the medium for this intense $\pi-\pi^*$ transition. The oscillator strengths and the natural radiative lifetimes T_N have been calculated from the integrated area under the absorption curves and compared with the average life T as obtained from phase-shift method previously. The results suggest that the dipole moment of fluorescein anion is slightly smaller in the excited state. This may be a probable reason for the observed blue-shift.

The lifetime of an excited state of a fluorescent molecule is defined as the time taken for the emitted intensity, I , to drop to $\frac{1}{e}$ th of its value I_0 when the incident radiation has been cut off after establishment of the photostationary equilibrium. It is inversely related to the spontaneous transition probability of a molecule from a higher excited state to all the vibration-rotation levels of the ground state which in turn is governed by the oscillator strength of the absorbing dipole.

$$T_N = \frac{1}{\sum A_{ij}} = \frac{1.50}{\nu_{\max}^2 f_{ij}}$$

where A_{ij} = transition probability from state j to state i and f_{ij} = corresponding oscillator strength = $4.33 \times 10^{-9} \int \epsilon_{\nu} d\nu$; $\nu_{\max}$ = wave number at the absorption maximum.

This equation has been derived on the assumption that all the molecules, excited to the higher energy level by absorption of radiation, revert to the ground state solely by radiational process. In such ideal cases, quantum yield (Q) will be unity. Therefore the values obtained by this method should provide the natural lifetime T_N of the molecule.

But in an assembly of complex molecules, this ideal value will not be realised due to potentiality within the molecule of losing the energy to the environment as vibrational energy cascade and finally to heat. These perturbations may or may not be affected by the nature of the environment². This will reduce the value of quantum yield to less than unity and the average value of lifetime, T , will be smaller than the natural value according to the expression $T/T_N = Q$. This mean life T of a fluorescent molecule under the experimental conditions of concentration, solvent, and temperature can be measured by phase-shift methods, using a modulated light source³⁻⁴.

A comparison of the lifetimes of a given solution obtained by these two methods is expected to provide interesting information regarding radiationless processes which compete with spontaneous emission process. Such an attempt was made by Gibson *et al.*³ for triplet state lifetimes of some compounds in solid glassy solution at liquid-air temperature. In the present communication a preliminary comparison is reported for fluorescein anion in alkaline solution for its intense ($\pi-\pi^*$) band in the visible:

1. Gilmore *et al.*, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1952, 20, 829.
2. Galanin, *Doklady Akad. Nauk, SSSR*, 1950, 70, 989.
3. Schmillen, *Z. Physik*, 1953, 135, 294.
4. Bailey and Rollefson, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1953, 21, 1315.

EXPERIMENTAL

The solutions of fluorescein in different solvents were prepared by taking 10ml of a stock solution of fluorescein ($c=1.002 \times 10^{-3} M$) in aqueous KOH ($c=3.14 \times 10^{-2} M$) in a 100-ml volumetric flask and making the final volume with purified solvents. This provided solutions in 90% solvent. Fluorescein (E. Merck) was purified by repeated dissolution in alkali and precipitation with stirring by HCl. The purity was checked by the measurement of molar extinction coefficient ($\epsilon_{490}=7.7 \times 10^4$). Solvents were of high purity and were further purified by fractional distillation. The absorption measurements were made on a Beckman spectrophotometer, modal DU, with photomultiplier attachment, using 1 cm cell with 0.9 cm spacer. An effective light path of 0.103 cm was obtained through the solution.

FIG. 1

—○—: H_2O ; —⊕— glycerol; Δ : EtOH; —⊙—: n -PrOH; —▽—: n -BuOH.

The absorption curve for fluorescein anion in a number of hydroxylic solvents is presented in Fig. 1. The absorption maximum in aqueous solution shows considerable blue shift as compared to alcohols and glycerol. Such a shift in ethanolic solution of fluorescein anion has been observed by Orndorff *et al*⁵. In the series of homologous alcohols, a small shift towards red is observed with decreasing dielectric strength from ethanol to n -butanol, accompanied by a decrease in extinction coefficient. In a mixture of glycerol and water, $\bar{\nu}_{max}$ shifts in proportion to the two components. The oscillator strength, f , was calculated from the area under the absorption curve, obtained by plotting molar extinction coefficient, ϵ , against wave number as abscissa. Fluorescein-anion absorption band has a series of peaks extending from visible to UV region. Absorption measurements with polarised light afford a knowledge of the limit of the longest wave absorption band⁶. Hence isolation of longest wave absorption was possible to a certain extent. The area was

5. J. Amer. Chem. Soc., 1928, 50, 819.

6. Pringsheim, "Fluorescence and Phosphorescence", Interscience Publishers Inc., 1949, p. 381.

obtained by using a planimeter. All the relevant data are recorded in Table I. The value of dielectric constant, D , for 90% solvent at 30° was obtained from the data of Akerlof⁷ and refractive index, n , was calculated from the mole fraction of the components in the mixture.

TABLE I

Solvent.	$\lambda_{\max}$.	$\nu_{\max}$.	$\epsilon_{\max}$.	f .	D .	n .
H ₂ O	490.5 m μ	20380 cm ⁻¹	7.72×10^4	0.59	76.7	1.3330
Glycerol (18.6%)	491.0	20360	..	..	71.5	1.3406
Glycerol (36.6%)	494.0	20240	7.59	0.56	66.4	1.3503
Glycerol (90%)	498.0	20080	7.44	0.57	43.5	1.4297
EtOH (90%)	498.0	20080	8.94	0.63	28.5	1.3539
n-PrOH(90%)	499.0	20040	8.57	0.60	22.5	1.3698
n-BuOH (90%)	500.0	20000	8.32	0.59	20.0	1.3755

DISCUSSION

The effect of solvents on the absorption spectra of organic compounds has been used to characterise the nature of transition involved in absorption process⁸⁻¹⁰. Blue shift with increasing dielectric constant of the medium are observed for ($n-\pi^*$) transitions, whereas ($\pi-\pi^*$) transitions provide a red shift under similar conditions. The longest wave strong absorption band of fluorescein is a ($\pi-\pi^*$) band. So this criterion fails in this case. There is no systematic variation with the refractive index of the solvent except within the homologous series of alcohols. In the case, where both solute and solvent are polar, such correlation is not always possible due to the fact that the superimposed influences of polarity and index of refraction can act either in the same or in opposite direction.

The natural radiative lifetimes (T_N) were calculated, using the values of oscillator strength recorded in Table I. For these transitions, the multiplicities of upper and lower states are both equal to unity. Refractive index correction has been taken as unity¹¹. The values are recorded in Table II. The third column in the table gives the actual lifetimes (T) obtained from the phase-shift method¹² of Bailey and Rollefson, modified by Kromman, under exactly similar conditions. These data were obtained by the author at the University of California, Berkeley. The accuracy of the method is $\pm 0.05 \times 10^{-9}$ for lifetimes of that order. Each value is an average of ten readings.

TABLE II

Solvent.	$T_N \times 10^9$.	$T \times 10^9$.	$(\frac{1}{T_N} - \frac{1}{T}) \times 10^{-9}$.	$\frac{D-1}{2D+1} = A$.	$\frac{n^2-1}{2n^2+1} = B$.	$A-B$.
H ₂ O	6.16 sec.	6.30 sec.	+0.0036 sec. ⁻¹	0.4904	0.1706	0.3198
EtOH(90%)	5.93	5.57	+0.0164	0.4742	0.1766	0.2956
n-PrOH (90%)	6.27	6.39	+0.0030	0.4651	0.1845	0.2806
n-BuOH(90%)	6.40	6.23	-0.0042	0.4635	0.1863	0.2773
Glycerol (90%)	6.56	6.12	-0.0110	0.4829	0.2053	0.2778

One interesting fact, which immediately becomes evident, is that whereas values of natural radiative lifetimes increase in the series of homologous alcohols to glycerol, the

7. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, **54**, 4125.

8. Forster and Konig, *Z. Elektrochem.*, 1957, **61**, 344.

9. McConnel, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1952, **20**, 700.

10. Bayliss and McRae, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1954, **58**, 1002.

11. Lewis and Kasha, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, **67**, 994.

12. Rohatgi, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1961, **217**, 353.

opposite order is obtained for observed lifetimes from the phase-shift method. The difference is positive in some cases and negative in others. In general, T_N should be greater than T , since all the processes competing with the spontaneous radiation process will tend to shorten the lifetime. A quantitative comparison between the two lifetimes cannot be made because of certain undetermined factors such as refractive index correction, overlap, and intensity borrowing between two neighbouring absorption bands etc. in the calculation of T_N . But the relative order obtained should be good. The positive and negative values for the difference then also become arbitrary; only the relative order is valid.

In the case of aqueous solutions, it has been observed by Bailey and Rollefson⁴ that for alkaline fluorescein solution, the average lifetimes obtained by the phase-shift method increase with increasing concentration of the solution instead of showing a decrease. They have accounted for this increase as due to overlap of absorption and emission band so that a quantum of radiation emitted somewhere deep in the solution is repeatedly entrapped before it reaches the detecting device. On extrapolating to infinite dilution, they obtained a value of 4.5×10^{-9} sec. as true lifetime of fluorescein anion.

Reasoning on the same line, it can be suggested that since for solution in ethanol a considerably greater difference is obtained for ΔT , the overlap of emission and absorption spectra should be even greater than that for aqueous solution and decreasing for *n*-PrOH, *n*-BuOH, and glycerol solutions. Since at the concentration of the dye used, the concentration quenching is negligible, this is the only effect that has to be considered. An evidence for greater overlap in ethyl alcohol solution has been obtained^{12a} from the measurement of average molar absorptivity for secondary fluorescence emission at various concentrations.

The overlap between absorption and emission bands is due to shape and disposition of the potential energy curve of the emitting state with respect to that of the absorbing state (Fig. 2). The variation in overlap in solvents under consideration is then due to

FIG. 2. Potential energy diagram for absorption and emission processes.

different amount of solute-solvent interaction in the two states. The effect of environment on the variation of (0-0) band separation as well as the red shift $\Delta\nu_A$ as compared with the absorption in the gaseous state has been explained by a number of workers¹³⁻¹⁴. Lippert¹⁵ and also Mataga *et al.*¹⁶ have independently worked out a theory for polar molecules in polar solvents. They have calculated the dipole moment of excited state, μ_e , from the known dipole moment of the ground state, μ_g , on the assumption that the shift in absorption spectra is due to stabilisation of ground state energy of the absorbing dipole by solvent-orientation polarisation effect¹⁷ on Onsager's reaction field and that in the emission spectra is due to its contribution to the excited-state energy. The difference in frequency of absorption, ν_A , and of emission, ν_E , of the (0-0) vibrational peak in solvents of dielectric cons-

- 12a. Rohatgi and Singhal, *Anal. Chem.*, 1962, **34**, 1702.
13. Sambursky and Wolfson, *Phys. Rev.*, 1942, **62**, 357.
14. Bayliss, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1950, **18**, 292.
15. *Z. Naturforsch.*, 1955, **10a**, 541; *Z. Elektrochem.*, 1957, **61**, 962.
16. *Bull. Chem. Soc., Japan*, 1956, **29**, 465.
17. Ooshika, *J. Chem. Soc., Japan*, 1954, **9**, 594.

tant. D , and refractive index, n , was found to be obtained, as a first approximation, by the expression:

$$\nu_A - \nu_F = \frac{2}{hc} \left[\frac{D-1}{2D+1} - \frac{n^2-1}{2n^2+1} \right] \frac{(\mu_c - \mu_g)^2}{a^3} + \text{const.} + \text{small terms}$$

where 'a' is the radius of the cavity; h and c have their usual significance. For polar molecules in weakly polar solvents, only the first term is important so that the plot of $(\nu_A - \nu_F)$ against the expression in the first bracket should provide a straight line.

If it is suggested that the difference in T_N and T for fluorescein anion in different solvents is due to overlap of absorption and emission spectra, it should be related to $(\nu_A - \nu_F)$. In Fig. 3 are plotted $(1/T_N - 1/T)$ against $[(D-1)/(2D+1) - (n^2-1)/(2n^2+1)]$ and data are tabulated in Table II. The points for alcohols fall in a line, but those for water and glycerol are scattered away. In more polar solvents, the neglect of small-range effects, such as H-bonding¹⁸ and association, may partly account for the deviation. In the case of glycerol, viscosity may play some part in determining the relaxation of the molecule in the excited state¹⁹.

FIG. 3

⊙—plot of $\left[\frac{D-1}{2D+1} - \frac{n^2-1}{2n^2+1} \right]$ vs. $\left(\frac{1}{T_N} - \frac{1}{T} \right)$.
 ⊕—Z-values of Kosower vs. $(1/T_N - 1/T)$.

The positive slope of the line in the plot will correspond to a negative slope for the original expression when $(\nu_A - \nu_F)$ is plotted. This indicates that the change of polarisability of fluorescein anion on excitation to the first singlet state is such as would result for a molecule, if the dipole moment were less in the excited state than in the ground state. This

18. Brealy and Kasha, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, **77**, 4462.

19. Lippert *et al.*, *Spectrochim. Acta*, 1959, **15**, 858.

can be expressed by saying that there is electron localisation on excitation. The various ionic resonance forms of this dye in alkaline solution can be represented as follows:

The dipolar structures (B), (C), and (D), which have greater electron localisation, will contribute more to the excited state of the fluorescein anion, whereas the structures (A) and (E) will contribute more in the ground state. This will result in the observed blue shift

FIG. 4. Plot of wave number of absorption maxima $\lambda_{\max}$ vs. Z-values of Kosower.

of absorption maximum with increasing dielectric constant of the solvent, in agreement with Brooker's²⁰ explanation for similar shift in some merocyanine dyes.

This conclusion also finds support from the recent work of Kosower²¹ on charge-transfer spectra of some pyridinium complexes. He has pointed out that the dielectric constant cannot be taken as an absolute measure of the solvent polarity as this represents the macroscopic measure of the behaviour of solvent in an electric field. His Z -values are a better measure of the microscopic solvent-solute interactions.

In Fig. 4, the frequency shift has been plotted against Kosower's Z values. The values for 100% alcohols are used for 90% alcohols and this has caused a slight curvature in the curve. The Z -values for glycerol solutions are not known. The observed positive slope again shows that the excited state of fluorescein anion has a smaller dipole moment than the ground state as explained for the pyridinium complexes by Kosower²¹. The difference may be small as the effect is small.

DEPARTMENT OF CHEMISTRY,
JADAVPUR UNIVERSITY,
CALCUTTA-32.

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20. Brooker *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, **73**, 5332.
21. Kosower, *ibid.*, 1958, **80**, 3252, 3261, 3267.